

GENDER EQUALITY IN THE ASPECT OF DIGITALIZATION

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Abstract. The article discusses bridging the digital gender gap in Uzbekistan. Rapidly developing technological innovations have a significant impact on the economy and labor market and have a high potential for social transformation. Digitalization brings with it many new opportunities in all spheres of life, including changing gender relations. However, it can also contribute to the persistence of existing inequalities, and in particular gender inequalities, creating particular risks for young women and girls.

Key words: digital economy, gender inequality, information technology, rights and responsibilities, employment.

Аннотация. В статье рассмотрено преодоление цифрового гендерного разрыва в Узбекистане. Стремительно развивающиеся технологические инновации оказывают значительное влияние на экономику и рынок труда, обладают высоким потенциалом социальных преобразований. Цифровизация несет с собой много новых возможностей во всех сферах жизни, в том числе изменение гендерных отношений. Однако она может также способствовать сохранению существующих форм неравенства, и, в частности, гендерного, создавая особые риски для молодых женщин и девушек.

Ключевые слова: цифровая экономика, гендерное неравенство, информационные технологии, права и обязанности, занятость.

INTRODUCTION.

Uzbekistan has already entered the digital era: we make purchases, pay for services and make an appointment with a doctor, communicate with friends and relatives via the Internet without leaving home. You can receive education remotely and use government services electronically. Adults do not need to carry a wallet with money, and children do not need to carry heavy backpacks with textbooks; instead, electronic cards and tablets are now used. Students send coursework, and scientists send their articles and reports by e-mail, including to other cities and countries.

Digital technologies have changed our daily life, study and work so much that it is impossible to list everything. Therefore, it is not surprising that in Uzbekistan, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated September 11, 2023 No. UP-158 "On the strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" [1], the Ministry of Digital Technologies appeared. His work will be aimed at "ensuring the accelerated implementation of digital technologies in the economy and social sphere," and consequently, the digitalization of our lives will accelerate. But the development of the digital economy in the country is not an end in itself. This is necessary, as stated in the preamble of the Decree, "in order to implement breakthrough scientific, technological and socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [2].

An important condition for achieving a breakthrough is the use of the labor and creative potential of the entire population of Uzbekistan, both men and women. Just as it is impossible to run fast on one leg, it is impossible to exclude half of the country's population from the processes of its technological modernization. However, on the way to narrowing the digital divide and fully including women in the digital development processes of Uzbekistan, barriers

may arise due to the fact that many basic problems of gender inequality have not been fully resolved in the country. First of all, they are associated with the underestimation of women's human capital (lower wages and problems with career growth) and the widespread prevalence in Uzbek society of outdated gender stereotypes about the roles of women and men in the family and society.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The rapid development of digital technologies and the active penetration of the Internet into all spheres of human life have led to the transformation of the labor market. Over the past decade in Europe, employment in the technology sector has grown three times faster than in other industries [3]. Experts from the World Economic Forum estimate that 75% of the fastest-growing jobs in the world require knowledge and skills in the field of STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics). There is concern around the world that the digital economy not only opens up new opportunities, but also creates new social challenges and risks.

One of the most likely social risks associated with the development of the digital economy is the growing gender inequality in the world of work and in society as a whole. First of all, the threat is seen in the upcoming gender-asymmetrical reduction in employment due to the introduction of new technologies, including robotics and artificial intelligence. In a report at the World Economic Forum summit in Davos [4], it was noted that upcoming changes in employment will largely affect women. It is expected that in the context of the development of the digital economy, men will lose almost 4 million jobs from 2017 to 2022, and women 3 million, but men will get about 1.4 million new jobs, while women can get only 550 thousand [3]. In other words, employment prospects for women will be almost three times worse than for men.

Job loss and difficulty finding employment will threaten single-income households supported by women and will exacerbate gender inequality. Digital technologies will primarily replace simple, routine jobs, but even such traditionally "female" professions as doctors, journalists, accountants, insurance agents or librarians can be partially or fully automated much earlier than one might think.

The problems of the labor market in Uzbekistan today are very acute; they are closely intertwined not only with the development of technology, but also with demographic problems. The reduction in the labor force that began in the context of demographic aging of the population has become a serious macroeconomic problem. The reduction in the total working-age population raises the issue of women's employment in the economy with all severity. Doctors, teachers, and service workers are predominantly women, and the Uzbek economy will not be able to cope without their labor in the context of the development of the digital economy. Consequently, for the female half of Uzbek society, issues of technological, economic and demographic development will be most pressing. The head of the Ministry of Labor of the Republic of Uzbekistan noted that "young families should not make a choice between work and family, both parents should have the opportunity to work, and the development of various forms of preschool institutions can help with this" [5]. It is probably no coincidence that at the state level, the development of the digital economy is placed on a par with the creation of employment opportunities for women. This could provide a chance for women in Uzbekistan who want to harmoniously combine professional work and family.

No less important is the question of the quality of jobs for women. What jobs will women get in the context of the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan? It is necessary for women to work not only in traditional sectors of female employment (education, healthcare and services), but also in jobs related to disruptive digital technologies. The digital transformation of the economy implies rapid development of employment in the STEM field. In Uzbekistan, women make up almost half of the workforce, but in STEM they hold less than a third of jobs. At the same time, an alarming trend in recent years has been the increasing masculinization of employment in industries such as communications and IT. Over ten years, from 2005 to 2014, the share of women employed in telecommunications decreased from 45 to 38%, and in IT - from 35 to 25%. The lowest proportion of women is observed among programmers (17%) and in organizations developing software and consulting on computer hardware (less than 20%) [2]. The displacement of women from jobs that require specialized technical knowledge and skills that are highly paid and for which there is growing demand could exacerbate gender inequality not only in the economy, but also in Uzbek society as a whole.

Today, the global community is concerned about why there are few women in STEM fields. In recent years, a lot of research has been carried out around the world and in Uzbekistan on how to attract girls to STEM education. The most extensive study took place in 2017, commissioned by Microsoft. It involved 11,500 girls and young women aged 11 to 30 in 12 European countries, including Belgium, the UK, Germany, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Finland, France and the Czech Republic. When asked what prevents girls from getting a high-tech education, "59% of respondents noted that they would be more likely to prefer a STEM education if gender equality already reigned in the relevant professions." Particularly high "uncertainty that men and women have equal rights in employment in this area" is observed among English women (70%) [5]. Thus, more than half of European girls do not want to go into the field of engineering and computer sciences, not because of a lack of ability and interest in mathematics (as stereotypes represent), but because of gender inequality prevailing in this field. The severity of the problem of inequality as a barrier to increasing women's participation in the digital sector is fully shared in the European Parliament. M. Gabriel, Commissioner for Digital Economy and Society, when developing measures to increase women's participation in the digital sector, identified three main areas of action: combating stereotypes, developing digital skills and education, and supporting more women entrepreneurs [4].

Modern youth, especially women, have to go their own way - from eliminating digital illiteracy to high professionalism and worthy positions in the new digital economy of Uzbekistan. At the same time, digital literacy does not mean the simple ability to use digital gadgets (almost 90% of modern girls can do this), but the ability to use digital technologies in professional activities.

And finally, the greatest hope is for the new generation, which has already been born "with buttons on their fingers", for which digital gadgets and tablets have replaced toys. It can be assumed that there will be fewer gender stereotypes in the socialization of the Millennial generation, since gadgets have practically replaced dolls for girls and cars for boys. There is hope that they will grow up different and will build relationships in a different (more egalitarian) way in the family, at work and in society.

CONCLUSION

Uzbekistan has already entered the era of the digital economy. But for its further successful development, it is necessary that information technologies be mastered not only by selected specialists, but by the broad masses of workers in various professions, not only men, but also women. Involving women in STEM employment is not an end in itself, but an economic necessity. The European Commission has calculated that if as many women as men enter the digital jobs market, this could create an annual GDP increase of 16 billion euros for the European economy [4]. Unfortunately, similar calculations have not been carried out for the Uzbek economy, but it is obvious that the underutilization of the labor and scientific potential of half of the country's population has a negative impact on GDP growth and the economic development of the country as a whole.

Strategies that will facilitate women's entry into the digital economy may include:

- coordinated and effective economic and social policies, the priority of which should be to combat gender inequality and insecurity as satellites of technological change;
- improving the quality of the education system so that it meets the demands and realities of a rapidly changing economy; development and implementation of national and regional programs to increase the involvement of girls in STEM professions;
- improving the collection and analysis of gender statistics, comparing statistical data on the education and employment of women and men in the technology sector; monitoring on issues of compliance with labor rights and equal treatment in the world of work, as well as on issues of creating conditions for women and men to combine family life and work;
- awareness-raising work on gender equality, aimed at overcoming gender stereotypes about the role of women in society and the family;
- technological retraining and tender education programs for school teachers and university professors.

Involving women in the digital technology sector will not only ensure their full participation in modern society, but will also give impetus to the development of the country's economy. The harmonization of gender relations and the elimination of inequality will contribute to the development of the personal potential of men and women. This is the key to the successful development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan.

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